

Temperature Impact on an Aerospike Nozzle Jet, a Computational Aeroacoustics Approach

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In this paper, the flow and acoustic characteristics of an aerospike nozzle jet at a Nozzle Pressure Ratio (NPR) = 3 and three different Temperature Ratios (TR) = 1, 3, 7 are presented. Implicit Large Eddy Simulations (ILES) are deployed to simulate the flow of the aerospike nozzle. The LES calculations are completed by aeroacoustic computations based on the Ffowcs Williams-Hawkings (FWH) equation. In the supersonic jet exhausting an aerospike nozzle, two shock-cell structures are observed: an annular and a circular one. In the direct vicinity of the annular nozzle, the annular jet is non-attached and reattaches further downstream at increasing distance with increasing jet Temperature Ratio (TR). The observed shock cells in the non-attached annular jet structure are longer for TR3 and TR7 compared to TR1. The shock strength in the annular jet is increasing with increasing jet TR. In the meantime, the total number of shock cells in the circular part of the jet decreases with increasing jet TR.

Pressure spectra in the near-field show the presence of a strong tonal noise at upstream angles corresponding to screech tones. Two-point cross-correlations of pressure data acquired in monitoring points located along axial lines in the circular shear layer are computed to quantify the upstream propagating waves associated to this tonal component. Power spectral density of the radial velocity at several monitoring points located at the shock cells as well as at the separation bubble, highlights the main oscillation modes of the annular shock-cell structure.

Supersonic convection velocities of turbulent structures are detected with increasing jet temperature by means of two-point cross-correlation. This confirms the presence of Mach waves observed in the instantaneous snapshots. The Mach waves radiation angles are in agreement with existing models. In the far-field spectra, the highest Sound Pressure Levels (SPL) are associated to those Mach waves at angles around 140° (TR3) and 120° (TR7). High skewness and kurtosis in the pressure signals indicate crackle noise at higher jet temperatures.

Additionally, the shock-cell length is used to predict the central frequency of Broadband Shock-Associated Noise (BBSAN) as a function of observation angles. The far-field spectra display mixing noise as well as BBSAN, related to the interaction between the convected vortices in the shear layers and the shock-cell structure. With increasing jet temperature, higher SPL are detected in agreement with the BBSAN central frequencies which were computed using the annular and circular shock-cell length.

I. Introduction

High-speed aircraft and rocket propulsion rely on nozzles to generate thrust. Circular, rectangular, twin- and aerospike nozzles have been implemented for propulsion engines since the beginning of their development. Nozzles are designed for a certain operating Mach number, temperature and pressure ratio often corresponding to ideal cruise conditions. However, real-world scenarios often deviate from these ideal conditions. In such non-ideal expansion conditions, the ejection of the hot gas triggers the formation of a shock-cell structure, which, in turn, leads to high noise levels. Several noise components with distinct generation mechanisms are observed in the far-field. Subsonic configurations exhibit low-frequency mixing noise at flow angles, attributed to large turbulent structures. In supersonic jets, additional noise components emerge, such as screech noise and Broadband Shock-Associated Noise (BBSAN). These noise components are intricately linked to the formed shock-cell structure. When flow instabilities are convected at supersonic speeds in the jet shear layer, Mach waves are generated. In highly-heated jets, crackle noise can be observed along the Mach wave radiation direction. All these noise components were identified in circular and rectangular nozzle jets at various jet temperatures.

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Mixing noise is observed in both subsonic and supersonic configurations. The radiation direction of this noise component is strongest around angles of 160° with respect to the upstream direction. It is generated at the end of the potential core by large turbulent structures convected downstream [1, 2]. The characteristic Strouhal numbers for these structures is around $St = fD/u_j \sim 0.25$, with D the jet diameter and u_j the speed of the ideally expanded jet [3]. Screech noise is a tonal noise component firstly detected by [4]. It is characterized by waves propagating in upstream direction in the far-field. The generation mechanism is the following: in a first step, turbulent structures are convected downstream in the shear layer and interact with the quasi-periodic shock-cell structure of the jet. In a second step, upstream propagating waves are generated. These upstream propagating waves reach the nozzle trailing-edge and impinge on the latter. The excitation of the jet shear layer by the upstream propagating waves closes the resonant loop. However, two distinct mechanisms for the generation of such upstream propagating waves exist [5]. In the first mechanism, the interaction between the shock cells and the turbulent structures convected downstream creates waves propagating in all directions and in particular in the upstream direction. In the second mechanism, the resonant loop is closed by neutral modes of the jet. In this scenario, the supersonic jet exhausting the nozzle is acting as a waveguide and the feedback acoustic mode closing the resonant loop is guided upstream along the jet [6]. These two mechanisms can exist simultaneously in a supersonic jet [5]. The generation mechanism for BBSAN is associated with the interactions between turbulent flow structures in the jet shear layer and the quasi-periodic shock-cell structure. It has first been identified by Martlew [7]. Harper-Bourne and Fisher derived a model allowing to compute the central frequency of this noise component as a function of the observation angle [8]. The BBSAN central frequency is a function of the shock cell length. Mach wave radiation from supersonic jet occurs when turbulent structures are convected at supersonic speeds in the jet shear layer. The generation mechanism can be explained by the wavy wall analogy where the latter consists of the turbulent structures in the jet [9]. The wavy wall travels downstream at supersonic speed and generates compression waves. The Mach wave directivity angle can be estimated by using the convective Mach number as in the model of Oertel [10]. Finally, crackle noise can also arise at high jet temperature. It is generated in the jet and can be amplified by nonlinear wave steepening effects [11]. Crackle is observed as sudden bursts in the pressure signals [12]. This sound component cannot be captured by classical Fourier analysis due to its non-periodic nature. High levels of skewness and a positive kurtosis of the pressure signals at monitoring points in the jet near-field indicate the presence of crackle. In certain cases, it accounts for 30% of the overall sound pressure levels along the Mach wave radiation direction [13].

All the aforementioned sound components are present in highly-heated, non-ideally expanded jets. The nozzle geometry, the temperature and pressure ratios at the inlet of the nozzle influence the intensity, the directivity and the frequency content of the various sound components. Several nozzle geometries have been used to maximize thrust. So far, conventional bell nozzles of circular and rectangular form as well as twin-nozzles have been deployed for aircraft propulsion applications. Engine manufacturers have investigated the flow characteristics and the aeroacoustic signature of such devices and come up with appropriate noise-reducing technologies. Aerospikes nozzles were implemented for rocket propulsion but their use in the civil domain is still limited, although they provide many advantages compared to the typical nozzles previously mentioned. For instance, they allow for an altitude-adapting thrust generation and a better thrust vector control [14]. Until now, most research about aerospikes nozzles has been performed regarding thrust performance and integration within rotating detonation engines (RDE) [15–17]. A recent paper is providing LES results showing the benefit of aerospikes nozzle for supersonic retro-propulsion [18]. One experimental study looks into the effect of aerospikes truncation on the sound pressure levels (SPL) in the near-field [19]. A recent work laid the foundation for an aeroacoustic analysis of such configuration in a systematic fashion [20].

A previous computational study on the aerospikes nozzle provided a reference solution about the important jet characteristics and the aeroacoustics of a cold non-ideally expanded annular jet [20]. Mixing noise, screech noise and Broadband Shock Associated Noise (BBSAN) were identified as the main sound components in the far-field. A model for the prediction of the shock cell length in the annular jet and the central frequency of the BBSAN associated to the annular shock cells was adapted from existing models for circular and rectangular jets [21]. The results provided by the model were in agreement with the shock cell length in the annular jet obtained from the LES calculations. These results lay the foundation for the present study on temperature effects. Generally, an increase in jet temperature leads to strong density gradients and larger convection velocities. A study on fine-scale turbulence noise from hot jets shows that large density gradients between the jet and the ambient air tend to increase the spatial growth rate of the Kelvin–Helmholtz instability [22]. As a consequence, the turbulent mixing and the jet spreading rate are increased in hot jets. On the contrary, an increased convective Mach number tends to stabilize the turbulent mixing [23] which counteracts the effect of the density gradient. Moreover, with increasing jet temperature, fluid instabilities in hot jets have a larger growth rate and a shorter decay time affecting noise radiation in the far-field [24].

A cold jet was considered in the previous study [20]. However, actual supersonic nozzles are operated at total

Fig. 1 Aerospike nozzle and annular chamber with relevant dimensions.

Table 1 Nozzle operating conditions and simulation parameters

Case	u_j [m/s]	M_j	T_j [K]	D_j/D_{eq}	Re_j	$\Delta t u_j/D_{eq}$
TR1	399	1.36	214	0.56	1.2×10^{-6}	1.41×10^{-4}
TR3	689	1.36	642	0.54	3.3×10^{-5}	1.83×10^{-4}
TR7	1070	1.39	1607	0.52	1.3×10^{-5}	1.26×10^{-4}

temperatures usually exceeding 2000 K. Experimental setups for assessing aeroacoustics of supersonic jets were reported for temperatures up to 1000 K (TR=3.4) [13]. Further nozzle development requires understanding of the flow phenomena at temperatures exceeding the maximal allowable temperature in experiments. Hence, numerical simulations are further needed to investigate the effects of high temperatures on the characteristics of a supersonic jet and the resulting aeroacoustic behaviour.

In the present study, the jet exhausting an aerospike nozzle is simulated by means of Large Eddy Simulations. The simulation setup is presented in Section II. The near-field flow characteristics with time-averaged flow characteristics are presented in Section III. The various noise generating mechanisms as well as the aeroacoustic computation results are presented in Section IV.

II. Methodology

A. Geometry parameters

Compressible Implicit Large Eddy Simulations (LES) of an annular supersonic jet with an axisymmetric, truncated aerospike nozzle at a constant Nozzle Pressure Ratio $NPR = 3$ and three Temperature Ratios $TR = 1, 3, 7$ are performed. A two-dimensional section of the truncated aerospike nozzle and the annular chamber with some characteristic dimensions are shown on Fig. 1.

The equivalent diameter for the annular section is $D = D_{eq} = 84.7mm$. It corresponds to the diameter that the annular nozzle would have for the same circular cross-sectional exit area. All geometric parameters in this study are made dimensionless using this equivalent diameter. The aerospike nozzle has a length of $2.08D_{eq}$. The annular chamber has a width $0.15D_{eq}$, as well as the nozzle lip delimiting the annular chamber. The relevant jet parameters are summarized in Table 1. Throughout this paper, velocities and Mach numbers will be scaled using the values of the jet velocity u_j and Mach number M_j , respectively, corresponding to the ideally expanded jet parameters.

B. Flow solver characteristics

Large eddy simulations are performed using an in-house finite volume-based compressible flow solver. The solver has been validated for a wide range of nozzle configurations and operating conditions up to jet temperature ratios of 4 [25–32]. Good agreements of flow and acoustic near- and far-fields between the CFD prediction with the solver and experimental data are achieved. An explicit four-stage Runge-Kutta algorithm is applied for time integration and a second order central difference scheme is used for spatial discretization. An artificial dissipation scheme after Jameson has been used and validated for different configurations to capture shock waves to avoid Gibbs-like oscillations near shocks and to relax subgrid-scale turbulent energy [25, 33].

Fig. 2 Computational grid for the aerospike nozzle with permeable Ffowcs Williams-Hawkins surface in white.

C. Computational domain and boundary conditions

A grid sensitivity study for the cold aerospike nozzle jet was performed [20]. It was used to identify the necessary grid resolution able to represent the jet characteristics relevant for acoustic analysis. The quality of the computation was assessed based on the length of the shock cells, the length of the potential core and the shock strength.

The axisymmetric computational grid is represented on the yz -section plane in Fig. 2 with the relevant domain diameters and lengths. The flow direction is the z -direction. The plane $z/D_{eq} = 0$ corresponds to the outlet of the annular duct. The computational domain is of length $65D_{eq}$ and extends from $z/D_{eq} = -8$ to $z/D_{eq} = 57$. At the far-field outlet ($z/D_{eq} = 57$), the domain has a diameter of $44D_{eq}$. The domain size has been chosen in accordance with previous studies of supersonic jets using the same solver [25, 31, 32].

A total pressure of $p_t = 304,000Pa$ and total temperatures of $T_t = 293K$, $T_t = 880K$ and $T_t = 2050K$ are applied at the inlet for the cases TR1, TR3 and TR7, respectively. At the outlet and radial far-field boundaries, the pressure is set at $p = 101,325Pa$, the static temperature at $T = 293K$ and the velocity at $u = 0m/s$. At the coflow inlet at $z/D_{eq} = -8$, a secondary flow with Mach number of 0.05 is applied. Adiabatic no-slip boundary conditions are applied in the annular chamber and at the aerospike body in a weak sense. Characteristic boundary conditions are used to avoid reflections [34] at the far-field boundaries. Additionally, a mesh stretching rate of 5 % is applied outside of the flow region to further dissipate the acoustic waves propagating and make the far-field boundaries reflection-free. Lower stretching rates would not correctly dissipate the propagating acoustic waves and larger stretching rates would lead to reflections from the grid directly [35, 36]. The same grid stretching strategy was applied in previous studies [20, 25–32]. The grid resolution in the potential core guarantees the propagation of acoustic waves at high frequency with a point per wavelength number $PPW = 16$.

To compute the far-field acoustic, the Ffowcs Williams-Hawkins equation (FWH) is solved. It requires data acquisition on a permeable surface enclosing the relevant acoustic sources. The surface is open in the downstream at $z/D_{eq} = 40$ to avoid pseudo-sound due to eddies crossing the surface [37]. The corresponding domain enclosing the flow region has a total length of $42D_{eq}$ and a diameter of $7.5D_{eq}$ at the annular duct outlet ($z/D_{eq} = 0$) and a diameter

of $15D_{eq}$ at the end of the FWH surface ($z/D_{eq} = 40$). The surface is shown as a thin white line on Fig. 2 with the dimensions mentioned previously. The simulations are performed for a total physical time of 65 ms with a transient of 15 ms. Data for the far-field acoustic analysis are exported on 364,000 nodes for a physical time of 50 ms every 2.5×10^{-6} s.

III. Near-field flow results

A. Instantaneous fields

The instantaneous near-field pressure as calculated by LES on the 140 million cells grid is shown on Fig. 3 for the three jet TR in the positive xz -plane. The formed shock cells in the circular jet are oscillating along the flow direction. Vortices of alternating pressure are generated at the outer nozzle lip (visible between $z/D_{eq} = 0$ and $z/D_{eq} = 0.5$) and are convected in the downstream.

The snapshots in Fig. 3 highlight some noise propagation features. The flow structures and shocks interactions in the annular jet at the outlet of the annular nozzle are producing acoustic waves propagating in the far-field at various angles. Upstream propagating waves originating from this region are detected. These waves might correspond to screech noise. Moreover, as shown in a previous study [20], a part of the waves propagating at upstream angles in the far-field are associated with strong radial oscillations of the annular shock-cell structure. The snapshots show that the amplitudes of these waves increase with the temperature ratio.

Screech noise has been observed in various studies [21, 38, 39] for circular and rectangular jets. It originates from the interactions between the vortical flow structures convected and developing in the jet shear layer and the shock-cell structure. Such interactions occur at the shock cell location along the flow direction and contribute to noise generation at a defined frequency. The acoustic waves generated propagate in the far-field in the upstream direction. The frequency can be estimated by the available vortex sheet models (see e.g. [21, 40]) The physical generation mechanism for Broadband Shock-Associated Noise (BBSAN) observed in the far-field [21, 41] is the same as for screech. In the present configuration, the interactions between shear layers and the shock-cell structures take place in two distinct jet parts; one in the vicinity of the aerospike bluff body (from $z/D_{eq} = 0$ to $z/D_{eq} = 2$), the other downstream of the truncated aerospike bluff body (from $z/D_{eq} = 2$). BBSAN propagates at angles close to the side angle (between 90° and 120°). A third acoustic component of large wavelength propagates in the far-field at downstream angles (close to 180°). This acoustic contribution corresponds to the mixing noise due to large turbulent structures. It has been observed in previous studies on both subsonic and supersonic jets [25, 42]. It is usually generated further downstream at the end of the potential core [2].

Strong pressure waves are observed between flow angles and side angles on Fig. 3b and Fig. 3c originating from the annular shock-cell structure. The highest intensity is observed for the TR7 case. This sound component corresponds to Mach waves generated due to the convection of flow structures through the shear layers occurring at supersonic velocities. An additional sound component of larger wavelength is observed for TR7 further downstream at the junction between the annular and circular shock-cell structures at $z/D_{eq} \sim 2$. This component could be related to Mach waves as well. A more restrictive pressure range makes visible weaker pressure waves propagating at side angles emerging from the circular shock-cell structure.

All the mentioned sound components qualitatively identified on the pressure snapshots will be analyzed in depth in Section IV.

B. Time-averaged flow fields

The time-averaged Mach number fields scaled with the Mach number of the ideally expanded jet M_j are presented on Fig. 4 for all three jets. An annular and a circular shock-cell structure is observed for the three temperature ratios.

Temperature increase affects the annular shock-cell structure. The annular flow reattaches on the aerospike surface further downstream when the temperature ratio is increasing (at $z/D_{eq} \sim 1.2$ for TR3 and TR7 instead of $z/D_{eq} \sim 0.85$ for TR1). As a consequence, the separation bubble trapped between the aerospike body and the annular shock-cell structure is elongated. This affects the dynamics of both the separation bubble and the shock cells and in particular their oscillation modes. Further results on the radial oscillation frequency of the annular shock cells and the consequences on the far-field aeroacoustic signature are presented in Section IV.D. The first annular shock cell is longer for the TR3 and TR7 cases compared to the cold case. The angle α formed between the axial direction (z -direction) and the center line of the first shock cell is increasing with increasing temperature. For TR1, this angle is $\alpha_{TR1} = 19^\circ$ while it increases to

(a) Normalized pressure field snapshot for case TR1.

(b) Normalized pressure field snapshot for case TR3.

(c) Normalized pressure field snapshot for case TR7.

Fig. 3 Normalized pressure snapshots fields in the xz -plane (140 million cells grid).

Table 2 Circular shock-cell size

L/D_{eq}	1	2	3	4	5
Tam's model TR1	-	0.67	0.65	0.63	0.61
LES TR1	0.74	0.67	0.64	0.62	0.57
Tam's model TR3	-	0.66	0.64	0.62	0.60
LES TR3	0.72	0.68	0.65	0.62	0.59
Tam's model TR7	-	0.66	0.64	0.62	0.60
LES TR7	0.72	0.69	0.67	0.63	0.61

$\alpha_{TR3} = 21.5^\circ$ and $\alpha_{TR7} = 22.5^\circ$ for TR3 and TR7, respectively. With increasing temperature, the annular jet in the vicinity of the nozzle is pushed towards the aerospike nozzle due to the lower pressure in the jet. Finally, higher jet temperature leads to an increased shock strength in the annular region. The Mach number jump across the first annular shock cell has a value of $\Delta M/M_j = 0.31$ for TR1, $\Delta M/M_j = 0.47$ for TR3 and $\Delta M/M_j = 0.76$ for TR7. Stronger shocks generally lead to increased Sound Pressure Levels (SPL).

Downstream of the aerospike body at $z/D_{eq} \sim 2$, a second expansion takes place and a circular shock-cell structure is formed. It displays ten, nine and eight shock cells for TR1, TR3 and TR7, respectively. The potential core decreases in length with increasing jet temperature ratio. The length of the first five shock cells in the circular jet is given in Table 2. The jet is not fully circular directly downstream of the aerospike bluff body (close to $z/D_{eq} \sim 2.1$). The comparison with the shock-cell length obtained with Tam's model [21] is made from the second shock cell where the jet has recovered a circular character. There is a good agreement between the simulated values and the prediction of the vortex sheet model developed by Tam with the jet parameters. The shock cell length is used to compute the Strouhal number of the screech and BBSAN components (see Section IV.B). A shock cell length decay of 3% due to the coflow at Mach number $M = 0.05$ is observed. This decay is in agreement with Andre's results [43]. Finally, as for the annular shock-cell structure, increased jet temperature leads to an increased shock strength in the circular region. The Mach number jump across the first circular shock cell has a value of $\Delta M/M_j = 0.09$ for TR1, $\Delta M/M_j = 0.15$ for TR3 and $\Delta M/M_j = 0.26$ for TR7. For all temperature ratios, the Mach number jump across the first circular shock cell is lower than across the first annular shock cell.

IV. Noise generation and acoustic results

A. Mach wave radiation

Mach waves are generated by turbulent structures convected downstream at supersonic speeds in the jet shear layer. Their propagation angle in the far-field ϕ is related to the convection Mach number M_c of the turbulent structures in the jet shear layer. It is given in degrees by the model of Oertel [10]:

$$\phi = 180 - \arccos\left(\frac{1}{M_c}\right). \quad (1)$$

The temperature increase leads to larger growth rates for flow instabilities. The convection velocity of vortical structures becomes supersonic and Mach waves are observed on Fig. 3 at observation angles between 150° and 120° . Cross-correlation of the axial velocity in the annular and circular shear layers allows to compute the convection speed of the turbulent structures. The results are shown on Fig. 5. Since there are two distinct shock-cell structures, cross-correlations are computed along two lines L_1 and L_2 located in the annular and circular shear layers, respectively. The monitoring lines are depicted on Fig. 6. Using the axisymmetry of the configuration, the computed convection velocities are averaged from data collected along four monitoring lines in the circular jet shear layer and eight monitoring lines in the annular jet shear layer. The velocity fluctuations are included in the convection Mach number profiles as thin dashed lines representing the 95% confidence interval for the computed values. The velocity fluctuations are increasing with increasing jet temperature ratio.

The normalized convection speed decreases with increasing jet temperature ratio. For TR1, the convective Mach

(a) Normalized time-averaged Mach number field for TR1.

(b) Normalized time-averaged Mach number field for TR3.

(c) Normalized time-averaged Mach number field for TR7.

Fig. 4 Normalized time-averaged Mach number fields for TR1, TR3 and TR7 in the xz -plane (140 million cells grid).

(a) Convection velocity (left) and convection Mach number (right) on line L_1 .

(b) Convection velocity (left) and convection Mach number (right) on line L_2 .

Fig. 5 Convection velocities and Mach numbers along monitoring lines presented in Fig. 6.

number in the annular and circular parts of the jet is smaller than 1. No Mach wave radiation is observed, which is consistent with the pressure snapshot shown on Fig. 3a. For the higher TR cases, the convective Mach numbers in the annular and circular shear layers exceed 1. These results confirm the presence of Mach waves observed on Fig. 3b and 3c. The directivity angles computed with the averaged convective Mach number shown on the right side of Fig. 5b using Eq. 1 provide angles between $\phi \sim 140^\circ$ and $\phi \sim 115^\circ$ for TR3 and TR7. The convection Mach numbers are higher in the annular jet shear layer than in the circular jet shear layer leading to Mach waves radiation closer to the side angle. The computed directivity angles match with the observed propagation angles on the snapshots and in the far-field spectra (see Fig. 14). The results are summarized in Table 3.

Fig. 6 Monitoring lines in the developed jet shear layers for two-point cross-correlation (L_1 and L_2) and monitoring points in the annular shock-cell structure for dynamics analysis.

B. Screech noise

Screech is a feedback mechanism characterized by the upstream propagation of acoustic waves through the jet shear layer. Two point space-time cross-correlations in the jet shear layer are computed to highlight these upstream acoustic waves. In the present work, pressure data were recorded at 96 monitoring points equally spaced in the circular jet shear layer ($r/D_{eq} = 0.45$). The reference point for the cross-correlation is set around $z/D_{eq} \sim 2.3$ depending on the case considered. The cross-correlation is computed along line L_2 located in the circular shear layer and shown in Fig. 6. The cross-correlation is performed between the chosen reference point and the other 95 points spread along this line in the jet shear layer between $z/D_{eq} = 1$ and $z/D_{eq} = 10$. The results are shown in Fig. 7. The x -axis corresponds to the axial distance along the flow direction. The y -axis corresponds to the time-lag in seconds. Negative slopes indicate downstream propagating hydrodynamic pressure corresponding to the convection of fluid flow structures in the jet shear layer. The maximum cross-correlation level is obtained for the reference point and corresponds to the auto-correlation of the pressure signal at this point. Periodic patterns with positive slopes indicate upstream propagating acoustic pressure. These patterns are only apparent at axial distances $z/D_{eq} < 8$, region in which a shock-cell structure is still present (see Fig. 4) and hence the vortical structures can interact with the quasi-periodic shock-cell structure. The time-lag for a single periodic pattern with positive slope is the screeching period. The corresponding Strouhal numbers obtained from the two-point cross-correlations for all the cases are summarized in Table 3. Using the vortex sheet model for a circular jet and the approximation for the first harmonic the screech tone of a circular jet [21, 44], the screech frequency assuming a circular jet downstream of the aerospike is the following:

$$St_{Screech} = \frac{u_c}{u_j} \frac{D_{eq}}{L_{circ.}(1 + M_c)}, \quad (2)$$

where u_c , $M_c = u_c/c_0$ are the convection velocity and the convective Mach number, respectively. $L_{circ.}$ is the length of the first shock cell in the circular jet (see Table 2). The convection velocity u_c is determined using cross-correlation for the axial velocity along lines in the annular and circular shear layers. It is presented on Fig. 5b. The averaged convection velocities, convective Mach numbers, circular shock-cell length as well as the screech Strouhal numbers for all the cases are summarized in Table 3. The results obtained by the model (Eq. 2) are in good agreement with the cross-correlation for TR1. For temperature ratios TR3 and TR7, the Strouhal number determined through cross-correlation is consistently half of the value predicted by the model. This implies the presence of various screech modes. Further in-depth investigations regarding those screech modes will be carried out in the Section IV.E.

Similar two-point cross-correlations were performed in the annular shear layers for 23 points along line L_1 shown on Fig. 6 for all three jet temperature ratios. A high-pass filter has been applied to remove the upstream propagating frequency component due to screech noise originating from the circular shock-cell structure downstream of the aerospike bluff body. However, no positive slope patterns were noticeable for the cross-correlations in the annular shear layer. This suggests that there is no feedback mechanism between the annular shock-cell structure and the nozzle lip and hence no screech phenomenon associated with the annular region of the jet located between $0 < z/D_{eq} < 2$.

(a) Normalized two-point cross-correlation in the circular jet shear layers along L_2 for TR1.

(b) Normalized two-point cross-correlation in the circular jet shear layers along L_2 for TR3.

(c) Normalized two-point cross-correlation in the circular jet shear layers along L_2 for TR7.

Fig. 7 Normalized two-point cross-correlations in the jet shear layers along line L_2 for the three jet temperature ratios.

C. Shock-cell structure of the annular jet

The shock cell length in the potential core is related to the central frequencies of BBSAN and screech as seen in Eq. 2 according to [21]. Thus, the correct prediction of the shock cell length is crucial for far-field noise computation. In the baseline study, a vortex sheet model tailored to the annular part of the jet is deployed to predict the length $L_{ann.}$ of the annular shock cells [20]. This model can be extended to higher temperature ratio cases. The results are given in Table 4.

The flow is reattaching on the aerospike bluff body further downstream at location $z/D_{eq} \sim 1.2$ at higher temperature

Table 3 Normalized convection velocities, convection Mach numbers, Mach waves propagation angles, screech Strouhal number $St_{Screech}$ predicted by Eq. 2 and $St_{up.}$ of the upstream propagating waves identified on the two-point cross-correlations in the shear layers (Fig. 7).

Case	$u_c/u_j (L_1)$	$u_c/u_j (L_2)$	$M_c (L_1)$	$M_c (L_2)$	$\phi_{ann.}$	$\phi_{circ.}$	$St_{Screech}$ (Eq. 2)	$St_{up.}$ (Fig. 7)
TR1	0.84	0.74	0.98	0.87	-	-	0.51	0.51
TR3	0.81	0.67	1.63	1.35	127°	138°	0.43	0.22
TR7	0.78	0.61	2.45	1.92	114°	121°	0.33	0.17

Table 4 Annular shock cell size.

$L_{ann.}/D_{eq}$	1	2	3	4
Adapted VSM TR1	0.29	0.23	0.42	0.43
LES TR1	0.27	0.23	0.44	0.46
Adapted VSM TR3	0.32	0.25	0.24	0.46
LES TR3	0.34	0.24	0.24	0.44
Adapted VSM TR7	0.33	0.27	0.22	0.42
LES TR7	0.37	0.27	0.23	0.46

ratios compared to the cold case. This delayed reattachment leads to longer shock cells. At TR1, the first two shock cells belong to the non-attached part (up to $z/D_{eq} \sim 0.85$) of the flow and two shock cells belong to the attached part. At higher TR, the first three shock cells belong to the non-attached part (up to $z/D_{eq} \sim 1.2$). Furthermore, the delayed flow reattachment leads to longer shock cells. The length $L_{ann.}$ predicted by the adapted vortex sheet model (VSM) is in good agreement with the simulation results. For TR1, the length of the first shock cell is overpredicted while it is underpredicted for the TR3 and TR7. This underprediction may be due to the change of inclination angle α with respect to the flow direction (z -direction) due to the higher jet temperature. The used vortex sheet model assumes low inclination angles of the shock cells with respect to the flow direction.

D. Oscillation modes of the annular jet

Power spectral density of the radial velocity component is computed at relevant points in the annular jet to identify its oscillation modes. The points are shown on Fig. 6. P_1 is located at the separation bubble, P_2 is located at the junction between the expansion cell at the outlet of the annular chamber and the first shock cell, P_3 is located between the two first shock cells. It is worth noting that the annular shock-cell structure differs from case to case (see e.g. Fig. 4). Additionally, the separation bubble is longer for higher TR. Hence, the position of the separation bubble and the shock cells varies slightly. Therefore, the points considered for the oscillation mode analysis need to be adjusted depending on the temperature case. The range for the Strouhal number $St = fD_{eq}/u_j$ varies for each temperature case since u_j increases with increasing jet temperature.

The power spectral density results are shown on Fig. 8. The TR1 case (Fig. 8a) displays a main radial oscillation mode at $St \sim 1.25$ for the separation bubble and the annular shock cells. It exhibits a broadband character. The spectra display additional peaks at $St = 0.52$ and $St = 0.68$. These peaks were identified in a previous study with a finer mesh [20]. At the screech frequency, the circular part of the jet is subject to a strong flapping motion. The upstream propagating waves originating from the circular part of the jet interact with the annular shock-cell structure and excite the latter. This explains the peaks at $St = 0.52$ for TR1, $St = 0.43$ for TR3 and $St = 0.38$ for TR7. The peaks are clearer for the shock cells than for the separation bubble. The radial oscillations of the separation bubble are linked to the oscillation of both first shock cells.

The power spectra density of the radial velocity component for the TR3 case at the three monitoring points is shown in Fig. 8b. Strong oscillations for the annular shock-cell structure are detected at Strouhal numbers $St = \{1.17, 1.32, 1.40, 1.56\}$. Peaks at these Strouhal numbers are detected in the far-field spectrum for TR3 (see Fig.

Fig. 8 Power spectral density for the radial velocity for the three jet temperature ratios at the location of the separation bubble (P_1), the junction between the expansion cell and the first annular shock cell (P_2) and the junction of the two first annular shock cells (P_3).

14b). A further peak is identified at $St = 0.43$ which corresponds to the screech frequency computed using Eq. 2. The power spectral density for point P_3 located between the first and second shock cell shows peaks at comparable magnitudes. This observation does not provide sufficient information to draw conclusions regarding the dynamics of the annular jet further downstream.

For the TR7 case, the clearest peak is found for P_2 at a Strouhal number $St = 1.07$. It corresponds to the main oscillation mode of the annular shock-cell structure. This peak is found on the spectra for P_3 and P_1 but at a lower intensity level. It has a slight broadband character with a bandwidth around $\Delta St = 0.08$. Secondary peaks at $St = 0.38$ and $St = 1.24$ are observed for the shock cells (points P_2 and P_3). The oscillation at $St = 0.38$ is due to the coupling with the screech noise generated in the circular part of the jet downstream. On the other hand, the separation bubble displays an important oscillation mode at $St = 0.79$. This suggests that it is linked with an eigenmode of the separation bubble rather than an oscillation mode of the shock-cell structure. It is expected to observe high SPL at these Strouhal numbers in the far-field spectra.

E. Vortex sheet model: Neutral modes of the circular jet

For the higher temperature cases, the Strouhal numbers computed for the upstream propagating modes using the two-point cross-correlations (see Fig. 7) correspond to half of the Strouhal numbers computed with Eq. 2, that are also observed in the far-field on Fig. 14 at upstream angles. For TR1, the two-point cross-correlation provides the same Strouhal number as computed with Eq. 2. On the one hand, it is known that screech noise is associated with

strong oscillations of the jet. These oscillations can be axisymmetric or helical in the case of a circular jet [45]. On the other hand, it is also known that there are two mechanisms leading to screech noise. The first mechanism has already been presented and used in the first study on the cold aerospace nozzle jet [20]. It corresponds to the limit of the BBSAN component for $\theta = \pi$ and is called the weakest link model [40, 41]. In that case, the feedback loop is closed by freely propagating acoustic waves generated by the interaction between the shock-cell structure and vortices convected downstream. However, it was shown that upstream propagating waves related to screech also correspond to the neutral modes of the jet acting as a waveguide. These neutral waves propagating upstream can close the feedback loop responsible for screech noise. In a non-ideally expanded jet, these two mechanisms can coexist. Let us identify the type of waves associated with these strong oscillations.

Fig. 9 Frequency-wave-number spectra of pressure fluctuations at **a,b** $r = 0.4D_{eq}$, **c,d** $r = 0.6D_{eq}$ and **e,f** $r = 0.8D_{eq}$ for modes **a,c,e** $n = 0$ and **b,d,f** $n = 1$; (solid lines) dispersion relations of the axisymmetric (left) and helical (right) neutral acoustic modes for TR1; (dashed) $k = -\omega/a_0$.

Neutral waves have a real wave number k and a real frequency ω . The dispersion relation of these instability waves is found by using a vortex sheet model of the jets as proposed by Lessen et al. [46]. For a circular jet characterized by the jet diameter D_{eq} , the velocity u_j and Mach number M_j of the ideally expanded jet, the dispersion relation for the

Fig. 10 Frequency-wave-number spectra of pressure fluctuations at a,b) $r = 0.4D_{eq}$ and c,d) $r = 0.6D_{eq}$ for modes a,c) $n = 0$ and b,d) $n = 1$; (solid lines) dispersion relations of the axisymmetric (left) and helical (right) neutral acoustic modes for TR3; (dashed) $k = -\omega/a_0$.

neutral waves is the following:

$$|\xi_+|J_n(|\xi_-\alpha|)\frac{K_{n-1}(|\xi_+\alpha|) + K_{n+1}(|\xi_+\alpha|)}{K_n(|\xi_+\alpha|)} + \frac{C^2|\xi_-|}{\left(\frac{a_0C}{a_j} - M_j\right)^2} [J_{n-1}(|\xi_-\alpha|) - J_{n+1}(|\xi_-\alpha|)] = 0, \quad (3)$$

where a_0 and a_j are the speeds of sound in the ambient air and in the supersonic jet, $C = \omega/ka_0$ is the dimensionless phase velocity, with k the wave number, J_n and K_n are the n -th order Bessel function of the first kind and modified Bessel function, respectively, $\xi_+ = |C^2 - 1|^{1/2}$, $\xi_- = \left|\left(\frac{a_0C}{a_j} - M_j\right)^2 - 1\right|^{1/2}$ and $\alpha = kD_{eq}/2$ is the dimensionless wave number.

The neutral waves closing the feedback loop have a negative group velocity since they are propagating in upstream direction. Mathematically, this condition translates into $dSt/dk < 0$. A space-time Fourier transform has been applied to the pressure fluctuations at different transverse positions between $z/D_{eq} = 2$ and $z/D_{eq} = 10$. The frequency-wavenumber spectra obtained at $r/D_{eq} = \{0.4, 0.6\}$ for the axisymmetric ($n = 0$) and helical ($n = 1$) modes

Fig. 11 Frequency-wave-number spectra of pressure fluctuations at a,b) $r = 0.4D_{eq}$ and c,d) $r = 0.6D_{eq}$ for modes a,c) $n = 0$ and b,d) $n = 1$; (solid lines) dispersion relations of the axisymmetric (left) and helical (right) neutral acoustic modes for TR7; (dashed) $k = -\omega/a_0$.

are represented in Fig. 9, 10 and 11 for the TR1, TR3 and TR7, respectively. The dispersion relations of the neutral acoustic wave modes of the equivalent ideally expanded jet are displayed as solid lines. In the plane $kD_{eq} > 0$, the dashed line marks the convection of vortices at the speed u_c previously determined using the cross-correlation of the axial velocity and depicted in Fig. 5b.

Significant amplitudes in the frequency-wavenumber spectra are found for $r = 0.4D_{eq}$ around $St \sim 0.50$ for $n = 0$ on Fig. 9.c, corresponding to the second axisymmetric mode A2. High amplitudes are found for the axisymmetric and helical modes A2 and H1 on Fig. 9.a and Fig. 9.b, respectively. The corresponding frequencies are around $St \sim 0.45$ for mode A2 and $St \sim 0.33$ for mode H1, which are lower than the observed screech frequency. Moreover, the peaks at these frequencies are located below the region where $dSt/dk < 0$. This implies that these peaks are not corresponding to upstreaming propagating waves responsible for closing the screech resonance loop. It can be concluded that screech noise is due to an axisymmetric oscillation of the circular jet.

For the case TR3, significant amplitudes in the frequency-wavenumber spectra are observed for the axisymmetric and helical modes A2 and H1 at $r = 0.4D_{eq}$ on Fig. 10.a and 9.b, respectively. The corresponding Strouhal numbers are $St = 0.38$ for mode A2 and $St = 0.23$ for mode H1. The latter matches with the Strouhal number found in the two-point

cross-correlations for TR3 in Fig. 7b. This suggests that the Strouhal number $St = 0.22$ for screech corresponds to the first harmonic of the neutral waves of the jet which is a helical mode. Additionally, significant amplitudes are also found on Fig. 10.c for mode A2 at $r = 0.6D_{eq}$. This suggests that the Strouhal number $St = 0.44$ for screech corresponds to the second harmonic of the neutral waves of the jet which is an axisymmetric mode.

For the highest temperature ratio TR7, high amplitudes in the frequency-wavenumber spectra are found for modes A1, A2 and H1 especially on Fig. 11.a, 11.b and 11.c, at Strouhal numbers around $St = 0.12$, $St = 0.33$ and $St = 0.19$, respectively. The screech Strouhal number identified on the two-point cross-correlation (see on Fig. 7c) is in good agreement with the high intensity levels observed in Fig. 11. This indicates that the screech phenomenon could be due to an axisymmetric motion of the circular jet as in the cold case.

The high intensity levels observed are slightly exceeding the domains where the various axisymmetric and helical modes exhibit $dSt/dk < 0$, which would correspond to neutral jet modes closing the screech resonance loop. Right downstream of the truncated aerospike, that is between $z/D_{eq} \sim 2.1$ and $z/D_{eq} \sim 5$, the jet has not recovered a perfect circular character (see e.g. Fig 4). This domain of the jet corresponds to a transition region between the annular jet and the fully circular jet observed further downstream (from $z/D_{eq} > 5$). The slight discrepancy between the high amplitudes observed and the locations where $dSt/dk < 0$ in the frequency-wavenumber spectra could be attributed to this non-circular nature of the jet in close proximity to the aerospike bluff body. Hence, the vortex sheet model developed for circular jets might not be applicable in this particular region.

F. Crackle

Highly-heated supersonic jets are subject to crackle noise. This noise component was first identified by Ffowcs Williams [12] and is characterized by intermittent positive pressure spikes with a strong compression followed by a gradual expansion [47]. Several studies address the origin of crackle [11]. While it was originally believed that crackle was due to non-linear propagating effects in the freestream, more recent investigations show now that the characteristic N-shaped waves originate from the jet directly [11, 48]. Since crackle is not a periodic phenomenon, it cannot be detected by means of spectral analysis. Instead, skewness S and kurtosis K of the pressure signals are commonly used to detect crackle. They are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \frac{E [p(t) - \bar{p}]^3}{\sigma^3} \\ K &= \frac{E [p(t) - \bar{p}]^4}{\sigma^4} - 3 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where E corresponds to the expected value, $p(t)$ and \bar{p} are pressure time series and their mean value, respectively, and σ is the standard deviation of the pressure signal. Skewness characterizes the asymmetry of the signal; if it exceeds 0.4, it is a strong indicator of the crackle noise presence [47]. Kurtosis quantifies the distribution of a signal compared to a Gaussian distribution. A strongly positive kurtosis indicates non-linear N-waves that are characteristics for crackle noise.

Monitoring points along two lines are placed in the near-field where pressure data (see Fig. 12) are collected. L_{C1} corresponds to the propagation direction of the Mach waves emerging in the annular shock-cell structure for TR3 and TR7. L_{C2} corresponds to the propagation direction of the Mach waves emerging in the circular shock-cell structure for TR3 and TR7. The skewness and kurtosis along L_{C1} are presented in Fig. 13.

The pressure signals exhibit a skewness exceeding 0.4 for TR7 across a wide radius range. Additionally, within the same radius range, TR7 also displays positive kurtosis. These two features strongly suggest the presence of crackle noise propagating in the Mach wave propagation direction. For TR3, the skewness remains above 0.4 up to a radial distance of approximately $r/D_{eq} \sim 1.6$ but subsequently decreases with increasing radius. The kurtosis values for TR3 in this radial range are also positive but lower than those observed for TR7. Conversely, the data for TR1 indicates skewness and kurtosis levels that confirm the absence of crackle noise. These findings align with a previous study on jet noise that featured similar jet temperature ratios [27]. Insignificant levels of skewness and kurtosis were found along line L_{C2} suggesting the absence of crackle generated by the circular part of the jet downstream of the aerospike body.

G. Far-field spectra

The far-field aeroacoustic spectra are computed with use of the Ffowcs Williams Hawkins equation. The original formulation is found in [49]. Flow data is exported on 364,000 nodes located on the FWH surface (shown as thin white line on Fig. 2) every 2.5×10^{-6} s. The observation points are considered on an arc around the aerospike nozzle tip at a

Fig. 12 Monitoring lines for the computation of skewness and kurtosis of pressure signals.

Fig. 13 Skewness and kurtosis of the pressure signals along line L_{C1} shown in Fig. 12.

radius of $60D_{eq}$. The results for all the temperature ratios are shown on Fig. 14.

Strong wave radiation is observed for TR3 and TR7 at angles corresponding to the computed directivity angles (using Eq. 1) at low Strouhal numbers related to Mach wave radiation. The propagation angle exhibits a dispersion around a mean directivity angle, given the non-uniformity of supersonic convection Mach numbers for the different eddies. The broadband nature of the Mach waves in terms of frequency arises from the varied distribution in the sizes of the vortices convected downstream. For TR3, high SPL due to Mach wave radiation is detected between $St \sim 0.1$ and $St \sim 0.5$. For TR7, high SPL due to Mach wave radiation is detected between $St \sim 0.1$ and $St \sim 0.6$. Large eddies emitting noise at low frequencies are more effective sound emitters than finer structures. Hence, no high SPL is observed at higher Strouhal numbers. Generally, higher jet temperature ratios lead to higher SPL as can be observed.

Broadband Shock-Associated Noise (BBSAN) is also observed along and between the dashed, curved black lines.

Fig. 14 SPL in the far-field based on FWH equation at a radial distance $60D_{eq}$ as a function of the Strouhal number St at different observation angles θ for the three jet temperature ratios. 90° corresponds to the side angle with respect to the nozzle exit plane while 180° corresponds to the flow direction.

The central frequency of this sound component is a function of the observation angle θ [21]:

$$St = \frac{u_c}{u_j} \frac{D_{eq}}{L(1 - M_c \cos \theta)}, \quad (5)$$

where L is the length of the shock cells (annular or circular ones), u_c and M_c are the average convection velocities and Mach number of the vortices. These parameters are reported in Table 3. The dashed, curved black lines describing the BBSAN central frequency as a function of the observation angle are plotted for both the annular and circular shock-cell structure.

Mixing noise due to large vortices is observed for TR1 at Strouhal number $St \sim 0.20$. This matches with previous observations [1]. This characteristic is particularly noticeable in the spectrum for TR1, as there are no overlapping Mach waves with the mixing noise in that specific case.

Additionally, high SPL are found at the Strouhal numbers corresponding to the radial oscillation modes of the annular shock-cell structure. The relevant oscillations modes were identified in Fig. 8. For TR1, the main modes were

identified at $St = \{0.68, 1.21, 2.59\}$. The peak around $St \sim 1.21$ displays a broadband character, which is in agreement with power spectral density of the radial velocity shown on Fig. 8a. For TR3, tonal noise is also detected at the various peaks identified in Fig. 10. However, it exhibits a more broadband character with respect to the cold case. High SPL is detected at Strouhal numbers between $St \sim 1.10$ and $St \sim 1.80$ which are marked in the spectrum. These sound components propagate at angles between 120° and 160° . For the highest temperature case TR7, high SPL are found at $St \sim 1.07$ as previously identified in Fig. 8c.

Moreover, a strong tonal noise component is observed at the screech Strouhal number for the three TR at the Strouhal numbers identified in the two-point cross-correlations (see Fig. 7) and in the space-time Fourier transformation (see Fig. 9, 10 and 11). These components are detected at upstream angles around 20° at Strouhal numbers $St = 0.51$, $St = 0.44$ and $St = 0.33$ for TR1, TR3 and TR7, respectively.

V. Conclusion

The effect of temperature on the jet characteristics and aeroacoustic signature of an aerospike nozzle was investigated by means of Large Eddy Simulations (LES). The far-field aeroacoustic field was computed using the Ffowcs Williams-Hawkings (FWH) equation. High jet temperature ratios affect the shock-cell structure of the aerospike nozzle jet. They lead to longer annular shock cells in the vicinity of the nozzle trailing edge. The supersonic flow reattaches along the aerospike bluff body further downstream with increasing temperature, as compared to the cold case (TR1). This leads to a longer separation bubble. Furthermore, the potential core downstream of the bluff body is shortened, indicating a stronger turbulent mixing at higher jet temperature ratio. The shock cell length is almost not affected by the temperature change in the circular part of the jet but fewer shock cells were observed. The temperature change strongly affects the aeroacoustic behaviour of the device. On the one hand, it leads to the appearance of Mach waves due to supersonic convection velocities of the turbulent structures in the shear layer. High SPL was found in the far-field spectra at angles around 120° and 140° for TR3 and TR7, respectively. Along the Mach waves propagation direction, both a skewness larger than 0.40 and a positive kurtosis suggest the presence of crackle for the highest temperature ratio TR7. On the other hand, the radial oscillation modes of the annular shock-cell structure are shifted towards higher frequencies with increasing temperature ratio. This leads to noise components propagating at angles between 100° (right angles) and 120° in the far-field. Broadband Shock-Associated Noise (BBSAN) was identified. The central frequency as a function of the observation angle of the latter was determined using an adapted vortex sheet model for the annular part of the jet. The simulation results compare well with the vortex sheet model developed by Tam for circular jets [21]. This sound components propagates close to side angles. Two-point cross-correlations in the shear layers in the circular part of the jet allowed to identify screech noise propagating in the upstream direction. For higher temperature cases, the computed Strouhal number was half of what current model provided. To address this mismatch, space-time Fourier transform of the pressure signals were computed in the shear layers to identify the neutral modes of the jet. It was found that screech noise in the coldest and hottest case was mainly linked to an axisymmetric oscillation of the circular jet while an additional component related to an helical mode was emerging for the middle temperature ratio TR3.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the "INSPIRE" EU Project H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020, Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Networks, Project No. 956803. The computations were performed on resources provided by the National Academic Infrastructure for Supercomputing in Sweden (NAISS, Project NAISS 2023/1-19) at the PDC Centre for High-Performance Computing (PDC-HPC) and at the National Supercomputer Center (NSC) in Sweden. The authors would like to thank Dr. Stefan Wallin, Dr. Peter Eliasson and Dr. Myeong-Hwan Ahn for the assistance of the code implementations and running the solver.

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